

PECHMANN REACTION: COUMARINS FROM 2-ETHYLQUINOL AND 4-ETHYLPYROGALLOL

BY D.H. MEHTA, R.S. SALIMATH AND N.M. SHAH

2-Ethylquinol and 4-ethylpyrogallol have been condensed with various β -ketonic esters and the respective coumarins obtained are described. The results show that these phenols are more reactive than quinol and pyrogallol respectively.

The Pechmann condensation of resorcinol and its various derivatives with different β -ketonic esters has been extensively investigated (Sethna and Shah, *Chem. Rev.*, 1945, 36, 1). Hardly any work on similar lines is available on quinol and pyrogallol derivatives.

Desai and Mavani (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, 15A, 11) unsuccessfully attempted the condensation of quinacetophenone with acetoacetic ester (vide Shah and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1425) and further found that 2-bromoquinol was unreactive; 2-chloroquinol was less reactive but 2-methyl- and 2-ethylquinols were more reactive. In the case of pyrogallol derivatives, the same authors (*loc. cit.*, p.1) found that generally they were less reactive than those of resorcinol.

The work described in this paper was undertaken with a view to ascertaining the effect of 2-ethyl group in quinol nucleus and 4-ethyl group in pyrogallol nucleus respectively on the Pechmann reaction with β -ketonic esters other than those described by Desai and Mavani (*loc. cit.*). On repeating the condensation of 2-ethylquinol with the β -ketonic esters used by the previous workers, we obtained the same coumarins; but phosphorus oxychloride was found to be a better condensing agent than sulphuric acid, used by the previous workers.

We have now condensed 2-ethylquinol (I) with (i) acetone dicarboxylic acid, (ii) ethyl acetosuccinate and (iii) ethyl- α -*n*-butyl acetoacetate in presence of sulphuric acid as well as of phosphorus oxychloride, the corresponding coumarins (II) being obtained in good yields with the latter agent.

[(i). $R_1 = H$; $R = -CH_2.COOH$. (ii). $R_1 = -CH_2.COOEt$ or $-CH_2.COOH$; $R = Me$.
(iii). $R_1 = n$ -butyl; $R = Me$]

It is thus evident that the reactivity of hydroquinone molecule is enhanced by 2-ethyl group, as borne out by the readiness with which it forms coumarins with various substituted β -ketonic esters, in comparison with less reactive quinol.

Similarly, 4-ethylpyrogallol was condensed with the above two β -ketoic esters as well as ethyl α -(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-acetoacetate. It was also condensed with malic acid in presence of sulphuric acid. All the new coumarins (III) and their derivatives are described in the Experimental.

- (i). $R_1 = H$; $R = -CH_2.COOH$.
 (ii). $R_1 = -CH_2.COOEt$ or $-CH_2.COOH$; $R = Me$.
 (iii). $R_1 = -CH(OH)C.Cl_3$; $R = Me$.
 (iv). $R_1 = R = H$.

The results show that phosphorus oxychloride is more efficient than sulphuric acid as a condensing agent. It effects the condensation with better yields where sulphuric acid fails. Desai and Mavani (*loc. cit.*) observed that the derivatives of pyrogallol were less reactive than those of resorcinol. '4-Ethyl' substituent, though not inhibitory, reduces reactivity of the pyrogallol nucleus as the coumarins are obtained in low yields.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Coumarins derived from 2-Ethylquinol

2-Ethylquinol required for this investigation was prepared by the Clemmensen reduction of quinacetophenone.

6-Hydroxy-7-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin.—To 2-ethylquinol (5 g.) and acetylacetic ester (5 g.) $POCl_3$ (5 c.c.) was added with cooling under tap. After keeping it at room temperature overnight it was treated with ice; the solid obtained was collected and crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 200° , yield 4.5 g., identical with Desai and Mavani's product (*loc. cit.*).

The *benzoyl derivative*, prepared by benzoyl chloride-pyridine method, crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 150° . (Found: C, 73.1; H, 5.3. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 73.2; H, 5.2 per cent).

The *methoxy derivative*, prepared by acetone-dimethyl sulphate-sodium bicarbonate method, crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 165° . (Found: C, 71.4; H, 5.5. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.5; H, 6.4 per cent).

6-Hydroxy-7-ethylcoumarin-4-acetic Acid.—To a cooled solution of acetone dicarboxylic acid from citric acid (12.5 g.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 25 c.c.) 2-ethylquinol (7 g.) was added in small lots, and the mixture was left overnight in an ice-box. On decomposing with ice, the solid obtained was collected and treated with sodium bicarbonate and filtered. The filtrate on acidification furnished the acid, which crystallised from acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 192° (decomp.), yield 7 g. (Found: C, 62.8; H, 4.7; equiv., 246.3. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 62.9; H, 4.8 per cent. Equiv., 246).

The *acetyl derivative*, prepared as usual, crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 182° (decomp.). (Found: C, 61.9; H, 4.8. $C_{18}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 62.1; H, 4.8 per cent).

The *methyl ester* crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 185°. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 5.1. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent).

The *ethyl ester*, prepared as usual, melted at 188°. (Found: C, 65.1; H, 5.8. $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 65.2; H, 5.8 per cent).

Decarboxylation.—The acid was heated at 195° for 15 minutes. After effervescence had subsided, the residue was cooled and crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 200°; mixed m.p. with 6-hydroxy-7-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin was undepressed.

6-Hydroxy-7-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin-3 acetic Acid and its Ethyl Ester

(i). To 2-ethylquinol (3 g.) and ethyl acetosuccinate (5 g.) H_2SO_4 (conc., 12 c.c.) was added with cooling; the mixture was left overnight at room temperature and then treated with ice. The solid was filtered off and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. A part of it dissolved; it was filtered. The residue was crystallised from alcohol in light brownish needles, m.p. 189°, yield 2 g. (Found: C, 66.1; H, 6.1. $C_{16}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 66.2; H, 6.2 per cent).

The filtrate was acidified and the solid was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in shining plates, m.p. 285°, yield 0.7 g. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 5.1; equiv., 261. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent. Equiv., 262).

The above condensation was repeated using 80% H_2SO_4 with the same results as above.

(ii). The above condensation was repeated using $POCl_3$, when a large quantity of the ester, m.p. 189°, was obtained.

Hydrolysis.—The ester was hydrolysed by alcoholic sodium hydroxide (10%) when the acid, m.p. 285°, was obtained, identical with the acid described above.

Derivatives of the Ester.—The *acetyl derivative*, crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 126°. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 5.9. $C_{18}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 65.1; H, 6.0 per cent).

The *benzoyl derivative* crystallised from alcohol in long needles, m.p. 145°. (Found: C, 70.1; H, 5.6. $C_{23}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 70.0; H, 5.6 per cent).

The *methoxy derivative*, prepared as usual, crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 169°. (Found: C, 66.7; H, 6.5. $C_{17}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 67.1; H, 6.6 per cent).

Derivatives of the Acid.—The *ethyl ester* was found identical with the above condensation product. The *acetyl derivative* crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 215°. (Found: C, 62.9; H, 5.2. $C_{16}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 63.2; H, 5.3 per cent).

The *decarboxylation* was carried out as before. The product, m.p. 245°, was found identical with 6-hydroxy-7-ethyl-3:4-dimethylcoumarin.

6-Hydroxy-7-ethyl-3:4-dimethylcoumarin.—2-Ethylquinol (3 g.) and ethyl- α -methyl acetoacetate (4 g.) were treated with $POCl_3$ (3 c.c.) with cooling under tap. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature and then poured over ice. A solid separating, was crystallised from alcohol in white plates, m.p. 245°, yield 3 g. Desai and Mavani (*loc. cit.*) report m.p. 239°. (Found: C, 71.3; H, 6.3. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$: C, 71.6; H, 6.4 per cent).

The *acetyl derivative* crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 149°. Desai and Mavani (*loc. cit.*) report m.p. 150°.

The *benzoyl derivative* was obtained in white needles from alcohol, m.p. 137°. Found: C, 74.5; H, 5.5. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 74.5; H, 5.6 per cent).

The *methoxy derivative* crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 188°. (Found: C, 72.8; H, 6.9. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.0; H, 7.0 per cent).

6-Hydroxy-7-phenyl-4-methylcoumarin.—2-Ethylquinol (3 g.) was condensed with ethyl benzoylacetate (5 g.) in presence of $POCl_3$. The product crystallised from benzene in light green needles, m.p. 194°, yield 1.5 g. Desai and Mavani (*loc. cit.*) report the same melting point.

The *acetyl derivative* was obtained in buff-coloured needles from alcohol, m.p. 125°. (Found: C, 73.2; H, 5.2. $C_{16}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 73.4; H, 5.2 per cent).

6-Hydroxy-7-ethyl-3-butyl-4-methylcoumarin.—2-Ethylquinol (3 g.) was condensed with ethyl- α -*n*-butyl acetoacetate (4 g.) as before. On working up the reaction mixture after 2 days, the pasty product on repeated washing with cold water afforded a solid which crystallised from benzene in light green grains, m.p. 215°, yield 2 g. (Found: C, 73.8; H, 7.7. $C_{18}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 73.8; H, 7.7 per cent).

The *acetyl derivative* crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 150°. (Found: C, 71.3; H, 7.0. $C_{16}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 71.5; H, 7.3 per cent).

Coumarins derived from 4-Ethylpyrogallol

4-Ethylpyrogallol was prepared by the Clemmensen reduction of gallacetophenone. 4-Ethylpyrogallol on condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of (i) $AlCl_3$ in nitrobenzene and (ii) $POCl_3$ yielded 7:8-dihydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin, m.p. 204°. Desai and Mavani (*loc. cit.*, p. 4) report the same melting point.

Formation of 7:8-Dihydroxy-6-ethylcoumarin-4-acetic Acid.—To ice-cooled acetone dicarboxylic acid from citric acid (8 g.) and H_2SO_4 (10 c.c.) 4-ethylpyrogallol (3 g.) was added with more H_2SO_4 (5 c.c.), the reaction mixture being left overnight in an ice box. On treatment with ice the product obtained was treated with sodium bicarbonate, filtered, the filtrate acidified and the resulting acid crystallised from acetic acid in long soft needles, m.p. 215-16° (decomp.), yield 2 g. (Found: C, 59.4; H, 5.0. $C_{13}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 59.1; H, 4.5 per cent).

The *diacetyl derivative*, prepared by acetic anhydride- H_2SO_4 drop method, crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless granules, m.p. 202-203°. (Found: C, 58.2; H, 4.8. $C_{17}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 58.6; H, 4.6 per cent).

The *dibenzoyl derivative*, prepared by Schotten-Baumann method, crystallised from alcohol in small needles, m.p. 110°. (Found: C, 68.4; H, 3.9. $C_{27}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 68.6; H, 3.9 per cent).

The *dimethoxy derivative*, prepared by acetone- K_2CO_3 -dimethyl sulphate method, crystallised from water in white soft needles, m.p. 112°. (Found: C, 61.2; H, 5.7. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 61.6; H, 5.4 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* was prepared by refluxing the coumarin-4-acetic acid (3 g.), alcohol (20 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (1 c.c.) for 15 hours. It crystallised from alcohol in long colorless needles, m.p. $212-113^\circ$. (Found: C, 61.2; H, 5.8. $C_{15}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 61.6; H, 5.5 per cent).

The *acetyl derivative* of the above ester, prepared as before, crystallised from alcohol in small needles, m.p. 100° . (Found: C, 60.1; H, 5.5. $C_{19}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 60.6; H, 5.3 per cent).

The *methoxy derivative* of the above ester, prepared by acetone-sodium bicarbonate-dimethyl sulphate method, crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 158° . (Found: C, 63.5; H, 6.1. $C_{17}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 63.7; H, 6.2 per cent).

4-Ethylpyrogallol was condensed with ethyl acetosuccinate in presence of (i) H_2SO_4 (80%) and (ii) $POCl_3$. The yield is poor in (i) and nearly quantitative in (ii). Ethyl 7:8-dihydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate crystallised from benzene in colorless-needles, m.p. 152° . Shah and Shah (this *Journal*, 1942, 19, 489) have reported the same melting point.

Hydrolysis.—The ester was hydrolysed by HCl (conc.). 7:8-Dihydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic acid crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 275° , identical with that of Shah and Shah (*loc. cit.*)

4-Ethylpyrogallol on condensation with ethyl benzoylacetate in presence of H_2SO_4 (80%) furnished 7:8-dihydroxy-6-ethyl-4-phenylcoumarin, m.p. 145° (Desai and Mavani, *loc. cit.*, p. 4).

4-Ethylpyrogallol on condensation with α -(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloro-ethyl)-acetoacetate in presence of $POCl_3$ afforded 7:8-dihydroxy-6-ethyl-3-(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloro-ethyl)-4-methylcoumarin, identical with that of Shah and Kulkarni (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1941, 10, Pt. III, 120).

The *tribenzoyl derivative*, prepared by Schotten-Baumann method, crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless granules, m.p. 103° . (Found: C, 61.6; H, 3.5. $C_{35}H_{25}O_5Cl_3$ requires C, 61.8; H, 3.7 per cent).

The *trimethoxy derivative*, prepared as before, crystallised from alcohol in small needles, m.p. $144-45^\circ$. (Found: C, 49.6; H, 4.5. $C_{17}H_{16}O_8Cl_3$ requires C, 49.8; H, 4.6 per cent).

Condensation of 4-Ethylpyrogallol with Malic Acid

4-Ethylpyrogallol (3 g.), malic (3 g.) and H_2SO_4 (20 c.c.) were mixed and heated on a water-bath for 1 hour. On treating the mixture with water, the mass became pasty which was repeatedly washed with cold water. On crystallisation first from dilute alcohol and then from water, pale yellow needles were obtained, m.p. $171-72^\circ$, yield 1 g. (Found: C, 63.8; H, 4.6. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.1; H, 4.8 per cent).

The *diacetyl derivative*, prepared by acetic anhydride—NaAc method, crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 140° . (Found: C, 64.1; H, 4.9. $C_{15}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 64.3; H, 5.0 per cent).